

Ayodhya's Keertan Tradition and Its Socio-Cultural Aspects and Connections

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Abstract

Ayodhya's rich musical heritage originated and flourished within the saint communities (Sant Samaj), where vocal music traditions such as Dhrupad, Khayal, Bhajan, and Keertan have been preserved and continued in temples. The Ramanandi sampradaya's three prominent sections Bindu Sampradaya, Akhada Sampradaya and Rasik Sampradaya have played a central role in Ayodhya's Keertan tradition. Saint musicians (Sant Sangeetaga), associated with these three sampradayas, created a vast repertoire of Pad and Padavali dedicated to Sri Ram and Janki. This research finds a research gap in Ayodhya's classical and folk music; the Keertan Parampara has received limited scholarly attention.

The present study investigates the unique characteristics of this Keertan tradition and its socio-cultural impact on the local community. Having been a keen and close observer of the Keertan tradition since childhood, the author brings a personal and intimate understanding to the research. The author adopts an ethnographic approach to studying this tradition in depth based on her experiences and engagements. By conducting in-depth interviews with Mahants of prominent temples and Keertankaars, as well as immersing in festivals, daily practices, and Keertan events, the research aims to capture the nuances of participant interactions and behaviours. This study sheds light on the unexplored dimensions of Ayodhya's Keertan tradition, offering new insights into its cultural significance and role in shaping the everyday life of the people.

Keywords: Keertan Tradition, Ayodhya, Indian music, Temple music, Saint musicians.

Introduction

Keertan (or **Keertan**) is a devotional practice in Hinduism that involves the singing or chanting hymns, praises, or the names of deities, usually in a call-and-response format. It is a key form of *bhakti* (devotional worship) that fosters a sense of divine connection through music and rhythm. *Keertan* is often described as one of the easiest and most joyful paths to spiritual progress because it uses the universal language of music, transcending intellect and directly touching participants' hearts and souls.

Keertan often follows a **call-and-response** format, where a lead singer, commonly known as the *keertankar*, sings a line or *mantra*, and the congregation or participants repeat it. This participatory style creates a sense of collective devotion. **Instruments** such as the *harmonium*, *tabla*, *mridanga*, cymbals, and sometimes the flute or other traditional Indian instruments accompany the singing. The rhythm and melody of the *keertan* play essential in invoking spiritual emotion.

The entire atmosphere of Ayodhya is steeped in devotion to Ram. Sadhu, saints, pilgrims and local residents walk from temple to temple, singing and dancing to the rhythms of *Kathik-s* and *Keertankar-s* within the expansive temple grounds. These joyous scenes are a common sight in Ayodhya. Saints emphasise that in the devotion to Ram, Naam (name), Roop (form), Leela (divine play), and Dhaam (abode) are all equally significant.

Local residents of Ayodhya take pride in the multitude of temples, often saying it's impossible to visit them all in a single trip. The music of Ayodhya has thrived primarily within the saint community, evolving from the dhrupad style through Khayal to Bhajan and Keertan, which continue to resonate in the temples.

The Keertan Tradition and Sampraday-s in Ayodhya

In Ayodhya, devotion takes on a unique form, as devotees don't view Ram solely as a deity but also as the king of Ayodhya. This perspective leads to a practice known as Rajopchar or Rajochit Upchar, characterised by obedience and complete submission. Devotees express their reverence with the invocation:

*“Nriya Geetadi Vadyadi, Puraan pathanadibhi:
Rajopcharorakhilesh, santushto bhav Raghav:”*

This translates to: "O Raghav! Please accept our prayers through dance, singing, instrumental music, and the reading of Puranas." Throughout the year, devotees offer Him royal treatment on various occasions, creating a vibrant tradition where devotion and submission beautifully intertwine (Sharanji Mahraj). The followers of the Ramanandi Sampraday embody the Dasya Bhakti bhava. Yet, differences in context, place, and emotional expression have led to various sub-sections, particularly in Ayodhya. Here are the three prominent sections:

Bindu Sampraday

Founded by Ramprasadacharya, this section is characterized by the followers applying a white dot (Bindu) as Tilak on their foreheads (Dwivedi 60). Their main temples are Badi Chhavani and Badasthan (Dashrath Mahal). They adhere to Ashtakaalik Sewa which refers to the services to the God performed at eight specific times. It is said that during Ashtakaalik Pooja, Swami Agradas would play the veena, becoming so emotional that he would start dancing. His ghunghroo (ankle bells) is preserved as a sacred relic. Temples in this section regularly organize music programs and keertan as part of their daily rituals.

Akhada Sampraday

The Akhada Sampraday was established to protect Vaishnavas from Shaivites (Saxena). The first akhada, Nirwani Akhada, was founded by Swami Abhay Ramdas in 1754 and is known as Hanuman Garhi (Dwivedi 61). Initially focused on combat and protection, they refrained from incorporating music into their daily prayers and rituals. However, influenced by the musical culture of Ayodhya, they gradually began to include music in their practices. In the two main centres of the Akhada (Hanuman Garhi and Khaki Akhada), they celebrate both Lord Ram's Aishwaryaleela (prosperous life) and His Shringar Madhurya Leela (love and affection).

Rasik Sampraday

This sect is dedicated to the *madhuropasna* (sweet worship) of Sri Ram and Seeta, focusing on their marriage and daily life through songs. Known as *Ram Sakha* or *Sakhi Sampraday*, they create and collect compositions that depict various aspects of Ram and Seeta's lives, performing *Ashtyam Sewa*. These compositions are often written under pen names that reflect personal relationships, such as being a wife, beloved, friend, or even a son. Some members consider themselves sisters or friends of Seeta, referred to as *Siyasakhi* or *Siya Aali*. Notable saint musicians adopt relational pen names, including *Swami Seetaram Sharan 'Madhurlata'*, *Swami Yugalanand Sharan 'Hemlata'*, *Jankivar Sharan Ji Maharaj Preetilata'*, and *Swami Ramshankar Das Pagaldas'*. Various other pen names, such as *Agra*, *Muneesh*, *Kripasakhi*, *Ramsakhe*, *Priyasakhi*, *Rasikali*, and *Premlata*, also appear in their compositions.

Among the diverse musical expressions in *Ayodhya keertan* tradition, several prominent forms of Keertan have emerged, each reflecting unique devotional sentiments and serving distinct ritual purposes.

Sri Seeta Ram Nam Sankeertan

Bhaktishastra emphasizes Naam Sankeertan, making Ayodhya the epicentre of this devotional practice. One of the key aspects of Naam Sankeertan is its accessibility; there are no restrictions on place, time, or materials needed to engage in it. The most prominent style in Ayodhya is the Sri Seeta Ram Naam Sankeertan (Dwivedi 79). Groups gather in front of the idols of Ram and Seeta, changing tunes as they chant "Sri Ram Jai Ram Jai Jai Ram" or enthusiastically sing the Yugal Naam Sankeertan, "Seetaram Seetaram Seetaram Jai Seetaram." Sankeertan is not just about name chanting; it also conveys significant characteristics, as in the lines, "Seetaram Seetaram, Sankat mochan jai Hanuman." Additionally, it narrates stories about the divine, like "Sri Ram Chandra Kripalu bhajumanu, Haran bhav bhay darunam."

Naam Sankeertan is performed daily, often in morning and evening sessions in most temples, while some ashrams and temples engage in continuous 24-hour keertan. Notably, Tapaswi Narayan Das from Bagahi Dham, Bihar, dedicated his life to popularizing Seetaram Naam across the globe. About 65 years ago, he established the Sri Seetaram Naam Ashram in Bagahi, Vrindavan, and Ayodhya and began running Seetaram Nam Rath (vehicles) to promote Naam Sankeertan among both devotees and the general public, encouraging people to dedicate time

in the evenings to chant Seetaram at home. This movement attracted many to the ashram, integrating Naam Sankeertan into their daily prayer routines.

At the Sfatik Shila Ashram in Ayodhya, Pn. Ramagya Das and Sri Sukhdev Das Maharaj organize the Seetaram Nam Jap Maha Yagya every two years, bringing together 1,500 Naam Japaks in 54 Keertan Kunj, huts where keertankars perform (Tatambari).

Since its inception, devotees have continuously engaged in Naam Sankeertan in shifts to ensure there is no interruption. Instruments like the harmonium, dholak, manjeera, and jhaanjh are commonly used. Keertanias sometimes wear an iron ring on their thumbs, striking the wooden part of the dholak for a stronger sound.

In other temples, Ashtyam Keertan Seva is also practiced. After Aarti, Naam Sankeertan is performed while sitting, standing, or during Pradakshina (circumambulation) around the Garbhagriha (sanctum). Morning and evening sessions often align with specific ragas. Notable texts like “Sri Seeta Ram Nam Pratap Prakash” and “Naamkanti” by Swami Yugalanand Sharan highlight the significance of Naam Sankeertan, serving as important resources for Naam Japaks.

Ashtayam Sewa Keertan

All acharyas of Rambhakti dhara described Ashtyam Sewa. Which is an essential part of Rasikopasak. Sri Madhuracharya described in his book ‘*Madhurya kadambini keli*’ about Sri Ram’s divine play and daily routine. Rasikopasak consider themselves Sakhi of Ram and Seeta, serve them in Ashta prahar, which is known as ashtyam pooja. The devotee in the form of a *sakhi* gets ready with all the *shringar* and imagines that the couple (Ram Seeta) are sleeping in *Kanak Bhavan*, and the *Sakhis* are awakened, guarding and taking care of the palace. After they wake up, *Sakhi* washes their feet, dresses them in a beautiful dress and ornaments. Take them to the dining *kalewa bhog*. During the course of the *Ashtayam Sewa*, devotees—assuming the devotional persona of *Sakhi-s*—perform various services to the divine couple, Sri Ram and Seeta, while singing context-specific *Pad-s* appropriate to each ritual moment. This sequence concludes with the *Mangal Arti*. Following this, the *Sakhi-s* symbolically accompany the deities for *Jalkreeda* (ritualistic water play). Upon returning and completing the *Rajbhog* (midday meal), the divine couple is offered rest. In the evening, the *Sakhi-s* awaken them with traditional *Padavali*, leading into the *Ras Kunj Arti*, after which singing and dancing ensue, accompanied by various instruments. Finally, once the divine couple retires for the night, the *Sakhi-s* resume their symbolic role of guarding the palace, continuing their devotional vigil (Sharanji Maharaj).

For each phase of the *Ashtayam Sewa*, specific *Padavali* have been composed to accompany the associated ritual activity. Several prominent temples in Ayodhya—including Janki Mahal, Manas Bhavan, Sadguru Sadan, Rajgopal Hanumat Niwas, and Kanak Bhavan—adhere to this structured eightfold daily worship system, known as *Ashtayam Pooja*. The sequence includes:

1. *Jagran* (early morning awakening)
2. *Shringar* (adornment)
3. *Rajbhog* (royal offering of food)
4. *Shayan* (midday rest)
5. *Utthapan* (afternoon awakening)
6. *Sandhya Arti* (evening prayer)
7. *Bhog* (evening offering)
8. *Shayan* (night rest)

Out of these eight ritual services, four are generally open to public participation:

1. *Jagran Gan* (morning devotional songs),
 2. *Shringar Arti* (adoration ceremony),
 3. *Sandhya Keertan Arti* (evening Keertan and prayer), and
 4. *Shayan ke Pad* (verses sung at bedtime).
- (Manasji Maharaj)

Manas Gaan or Akhand Ramayan Path

Manas Gaan is the chanting of the Sri Ram Charit Manas, composed by the renowned devotional poet Goswami Tulsidas, a key figure in the Bhakti Movement. This practice is believed to have originated with Tulsidas to invigorate a woman's husband. Manas Gaan, often referred to as Akhand Ramayan Path, is performed in two main ways. The first occurs during Chaitra Navratri, when devotees chant for nine days, culminating in Ramnavami on the ninth day. This form is primarily conducted in temples. The second style has gained popularity throughout northern India, especially after Ayodhya. In this version, devotees take a Sankalp (oath) and, through specific rituals, complete the entire path in a persistent manner. This call-and-response method involves performers singing 'chaupai', with 'samput' sung before and after each 'doha', often featuring lines like, "Mangal bhavan amangal hari, dravahu su Dashrath ajir bihari."

Family and friends of the organizer actively participate, enhancing the communal spirit. In Ayodhya's temples, Manas Gaan concludes with verses from Tulsidas's other works, including 'Geetavali', 'Kavitavali', and 'Vinay Patrika'.

Varshotsav

Ayodhya celebrates its festivals with immense joy, focusing on various aspects of Lord Rama's life. Different centres are dedicated to different occasions, allowing people to immerse themselves in the moments of their Lord's life—His birth, marriage, and the enjoyment of seasonal festivities. Devotees feel a deep connection, believing that God participates in these events alongside them. This vibrant celebration concept was introduced by the Rasik Upasaks, who have composed verses for nearly every event and festival. Their collection of compositions is organized around specific occasions, enriching the experience of devotion. This can be

illustrated through a chart that highlights the different celebrations and their associated compositions.

Month	Occasion	Types of padavali
Chaitra	Sri ram janm	Janmotsav Badhai Padavali
Shravan (July Aug)	Varsha ritu	Jhoolan Vihar Padavali
Aghan (Nov Dec)	Sri Ram Seeta Vivah	Maithili Vivah Padavali
Falgun (March)	Holi	Vasant Vihar Padavali
Whole year	All occasions and festivals	Panch Pallav Padavali, Dhaamkanti, Rasna Rasayan, Varshotsav Padavali.

The performative richness of Ayodhya's Keertan tradition is most prominently witnessed during its festivals, where music, devotion, and collective participation converge. These festivals not only commemorate mythological milestones in the lives of Shri Ram, Seeta, and Hanuman but also serve as active spaces for the musical transmission of Bhakti across generations. Building upon the earlier discussion of *Ashtayam Sewa*, *Naam Sankeertan*, and *Rasikopasana*, the following sections examine how these devotional sentiments materialise in different kinds of festive observances. The festivals are broadly categorised into three domains: those directly related to episodes from the life of Shri Ram and Seeta; seasonal celebrations that evoke nature-based expressions of divine play; and broader Hindu festivals reinterpreted through Ayodhya's local devotional lens.

Festivals Related to the Life of Shri Ram and Seeta

Sri Ram Janmotsav

Ramnavami is one of the grandest festivals in Ayodhya, drawing countless devotees from across India and abroad. Devotees begin gathering nearly a week in advance, and the celebrations commence with *Vigrah Shringar*—the ritual decoration and adornment of idols—accompanied by devotional singing (*bhajan* and *keertan*), primarily drawn from *Vinay Patrika* and *Geetavali*. The ambiance becomes vibrant with collective devotion and participation.

On Ramnavami, devotees crowd the temples from early morning hours. At noon, the announcement of Lord Ram's birth is marked by traditional musical instruments like *Naubat* and *Shehnai*. A unique ritual is observed at the ancient Hanumat Niwas temple, where a dramatic reenactment of *Ram Janmotsav* is performed. Artists portraying divine figures invoke Lord Vishnu to incarnate as Ram. The narrative depicts Lord Vishnu's descent first in his *Chaturbhuj* (four-handed) form, followed by his transformation into Lord Ram, wielding a bow and arrow. This moment is met with heightened emotional and spiritual

fervour, as devotees chant, “*Bhaye pragat kripala deendayala,*” enveloping Ayodhya in spiritual ecstasy.

The celebration culminates in the singing of *Badhai* compositions, such as:

*Sab mili aao ri sajni, mangal gaaiye,
Rani Kaushalya ke bhaye sut, vegi badhavo jaaiye.*

Various poetic and musical forms are essential to the celebration of Ram Janmotsav, including *Chaiti*, *Sohar*, *Sohilo*, *Badhai*, and *Rekhta*. Some notable examples include:

<i>Chaiti</i>	<i>Janam liyo Raghuraiya ho Rama Raja Dashrath ghar</i>
<i>Rekhta</i>	<i>Badhai Awadhesh ke baje, mano ghan gah gahe gaje”</i>
<i>Sohilo</i>	<i>Sohilo sohilo sohilo sohilo sab jag aaj,</i>
<i>Sohar</i>	<i>Chaitai kei tithi naumi tau naubat bajai ho”</i>
<i>Badhai</i>	<i>Badhaiya baaje aangne me”</i>

These *pad* (verses) are sung by *keertankars* and saint-musicians across temples during the celebrations. In the same temple, a *Seeta-Ram Jhanki* is organized in the evening, where artists dressed as Ram and Seeta enact scenes from their divine life. One important feature of this enactment is Ram’s delivery of the *Navadha Bhakti* teachings, to which the audience responds with great reverence, chanting “Jai Shri Ram” throughout the performance. The characters in the *Jhanki Leela* are regarded with the same sanctity as deities, reinforcing the devotional intensity of the celebration.

Janki Janmotsav

Janki Janmotsav is another significant festival celebrated in Ayodhya, marked by festivity and spiritual fervour. Similar to Ram Janmotsav, this occasion also features *Jhanki Leela*, although it does not include the preaching component. Temples associated with the *Rasik Sampraday*—notably Lakshman Kila and Hanumat Niwas—celebrate this festival through the singing of compositions by Rasrangmani and Chandrasakhi. A notable verse sung during the celebration is:

*Shri Mithilapur bajat Badhai,
Chaudah Bhuvan na sunti katahu as, Jas utsaah sajai*

Hanumat Janmotsav

Celebrated primarily at Hanuman Gadhi and Hanumat Niwas, Hanumat Janmotsav commemorates the birth of Lord Hanuman. Special *badhai pad* composed by Swami Pagaldas are recited during the occasion. A popular verse includes:

*Matu Anjani jaai lalan sabke sukhdaai,
Laal barann tan tej atul lakhi, mudit bhaye kapiraai*

Ram-Seeta Vivahotsav

Tradition holds that Goswami Tulsidas initiated the temple celebrations of Ram-Seeta Vivahotsav on *Agahan Sudi Panchami*. Today, this festival is especially observed in prominent temples such as Badi Jagah, Dashrath Mahal, Bihauti Bhavan, and Lakshman Kila. The celebrations span three days—from Vishwamitra’s arrival in Mithila to the Seeta Swayamvar.

Historically, performances included royal dialogues such as *Ram Swayamvar Samvaad*, *Ram Kalewa Samvaad*, and musical renderings of *Rasrangmani's pad*. In contemporary times, *Ramleela Bands* are often invited to perform. Numerous poetic compositions narrate the customs and rituals associated with the wedding ceremonies, including the *varayatra* (procession), *vadhoo aagman* (arrival of the bride), *mukh dikhai* (unveiling the bride), *kalewa* (ritual meal), and others. Examples include:

<i>Varayatra</i>	<i>Awadh nagariya se aili baratiya, mouriya pe ajab bahaar Aaj Mithila nagariya nihai sakhiya, charo dulha me badka kamal sakhiya</i>
<i>Vadhoo Aagman</i>	<i>Chali Siya aaju Awadh me aai Chandramukhi charo bahini gun, roop sheel chhabi chhai</i>
<i>Mukh Dikhai</i>	<i>Munh dikhai Siya ki ajab guinya, Kanak Bhawan ke ahaate me, bheer bhari hai</i>

Additionally, there are verses for everyday rituals and observances associated with the divine couple:

<i>Rathyatra</i>	<i>Rath chadhi chale Saryu teer, Rasikani Mithilesh Nandini, Rasik Sri Raghuv eer</i>
<i>Nauka Vihar</i>	<i>Nauka Vihari rahe Piya Pyari, Saryu john Jamini faili, Kumudini ki chhabi pyari</i>
<i>Phool Bangla</i>	<i>Phool bangle me sohe yugal rasiya, Phool ke haar hamel viraje, phoolon ki sohe naval pagiya</i>
<i>Khas Bangla</i>	<i>Khaskhas ke Bangle neeke chhay e, Nav Kusum Kali ke</i>
<i>Raj Singhasan</i>	<i>Singhasan Rajat Siy Raghuv eer, Kotin Bhanu Prakash Singhasan, Kotin Sheesh Sam Seer</i>

Seasonal Celebrations (Jhoolan, Greeshma Ritu Vihar, Him Ritu Vihar)

Among seasonal festivities in Ayodhya, *Jhoolan Utsav* stands out as the most elaborate. Celebrated throughout the month of Shraavan, from *Shravani Pratipada* to *Shravani Poornima*,

the festival features ornately adorned swings bearing idols and tableaux of Ram and Seeta in temple premises.

A major artistic highlight of the Jhoolan Utsav is the *Kathak* performance, which integrates *Katha Vachan* (narrative), *Nritya* (dance), and *Abhinay* (dramatic expression). Verses from *Vinay Patrika*, *Geetavali*, and regional folk traditions are rendered by Kathak artists before the deity. One of the most beloved verses from *Geetavali* is:

Dekhu sakhi aaj, Raghunath ki shobha bani

The musical and poetic ambience is further enriched by communal chanting of “*Sri Ram Jai Ram Jai Jai Ram*” while *Jhoolan Utsav* is particularly emphasised by the *Rasikopasak* community. Its devotional tone invites participation from a wider devotee base. Popular compositions including seasonal observances are:

<i>Jhoolan</i>	<i>Jaanaki Rasik sujaan Siya sang Jhooli rahe Jaanki Ghaat suhavan Pavan, Param Ramya sthan</i>
<i>Kajri</i>	<i>Hari Hari Janaklali Sang Jhole Dashrath lala re Hari</i>
<i>Basant</i>	<i>Khelat Basant Raghunand Chand, Raskhani Khuli Aanand Kand</i>
<i>Him Ritu Vihar</i>	<i>Asan Basan prati poos sukhari, Pahiri naval mridu basan jarkasi, Shaal Dushale jadi Kinari</i>
<i>Sheetkal Bhog Pad</i>	<i>Sheetkal Byaaruu Sarsawai, Haluwa vividh bhaanti ko saajai, Preetam garam suhavai”</i>
<i>Greeshma Jal Vihar</i>	<i>Uthi man jal viharani ki chahani, Mahal Sarowar Teer Khade Chhin, avlokani jal vahani</i>

Other Major Festivals (Deepotsav, Holi, Raksha Bandhan, Dashahara)

In addition to life-cycle and seasonal celebrations, Ayodhya also observes key festivals with musical and poetic fervour. Each of these festivals is enriched by regionally distinctive *pad-s* and *bhajan-s* that reflect the devotional character of the city.

- *Deepotsav* is celebrated with grandeur, transforming Ayodhya into a city of lights. Temples and homes are adorned with lamps (*Deepmalika*), and poetic compositions such as the following are sung:

*Saanjh samay Raghuvir puri ki shobha aaj bani
Lalit Deepmalika Vilokahin, hitkari Awadh dhani,*

*Fatik bheet shikharan par rajat, Kanchan Deep mani,
Janu Atinath milan aayo mani, shobhati sahas mani*

- *Hori (Holi)* is celebrated with the spirit of divine playfulness:

*Raghunand khelat Hori
Vipul sakhin jut janak nandini, baneu sakha hari or*

- *Raksha Bandhan* emphasises the bond of sibling love, as portrayed in:

*Sakhi lakhu Raksha Bandhan aaju,
Piya pyari ke kar kamlan me bandh rahe dwijraaju*

- *Dashahara* marks the victory of good over evil and is celebrated with hymns such as:

*Sakhi Vijay Dashahra aaju ri,
Siya Raghuvar ko suyash bhayo jag, dev dundubhi baaju ri*

Result and Discussion

Ayodhya's keertan tradition significantly impacts the socio-cultural framework of the region. It not only reinforces community ties and fosters individual spiritual growth but also contributes to economic vitality and cultural preservation. As such, it remains an essential element of Ayodhya's identity, continually evolving while retaining its core values and significance. The analysis of the Keertan tradition in Ayodhya highlights its crucial role in nurturing communal bonds and enhancing spiritual connections among participants. The call-and-response format inherent in Keertan fosters active engagement, transforming individual worship into a shared experience. Accompanied by instruments like the harmonium and tabla, this musical expression deepens the emotional impact of the hymns, enabling participants to connect with the divine in a joyful and heartfelt manner.

Musical Analysis of Keertan Compositions

Interpretation and Raga Framework in Pad Renditions

Most of the Keertan *pad-s* are performed in traditional tunes. Since the *sant keertankar-s* were classically trained, they composed *pad-s* in various *raga-s* and *taal-s*, chosen to reflect the theme of each *pad*. For example, the well-known pad “*Janki Rasik Sujaan siya sang jhooli rahe*” is set in *Raag Gorakh Kalyan*, while “*Balam sang Jhoole raajdulari*” is rendered in *Mishra Pahadi*. When discussing the ragas used in these *pads*, it is often emphasised with pride that “*our keertan is meant for the joy of Raja Ram, not to conform strictly to theoretical frameworks.*” Therefore, *bhav* (expression) is given precedence over technical perfection.

This approach is evident in certain *pads*—take, for instance, the pad “*Jhoole naval hindole siya pyari sang ban than rama*”, which gracefully weaves through the notes of *Raag*

Chhayanat, Desh, and Khamaj. Additionally, there is a notable *pad* based on *Mishra Khamaj* that is sung by different *keertankar-s* and singers, each interpreting it in their own unique way. While one rendition may emphasise the romanticism of the scene with elaborate melodic ornamentation (*alankars*), another may focus on lyrical clarity and devotional *bhav*, adapting the rhythm and *taan* according to the performer's style. This diversity in interpretation highlights the living tradition of Ayodhya's Keertan, where artistic freedom and personal devotion shape musical expression, making each performance unique and spiritually resonant.

Below is an example of a very popular *pad* '*siya rani ka achal suhaag rahe*' which is sung in a traditional tune as well as in other tunes.

Composition Style-1

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
						S	S
						<i>Si</i>	<i>ya</i>
G	-	M	P	M	G	R	G
<i>Re</i>	-	<i>ni</i>	<i>Ka</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>ch</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>su</i>
-	M	G	RG	S	-	P	P
<i>Ha</i>	-	<i>ga</i>	<i>ra</i>	<i>he</i>	-	<i>ra</i>	<i>ja</i>
P	D	S	R	N	-	D	P
<i>ra</i>	-	<i>m</i>	<i>Ke</i>	<i>Sa</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>pa</i>	<i>r</i>
P	D	P	M	GR	G	S	S
<i>Ta</i>	-	<i>ja</i>	<i>ra</i>	<i>he-</i>	-	<i>si</i>	<i>ya</i>

This tune is composed by Dr. Kalpana S. Burman, Ayodhya.

Composition Style-2

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
						G	P
						<i>si</i>	<i>ya</i>
D	-	Ṣ	Ṣ	N	-	D	P
<i>Ra</i>	-	<i>ni</i>	<i>Ka</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>cha</i>	<i>la</i>	<i>su</i>
P	D	P	M	G	-	G	P
<i>ha</i>	-	<i>g</i>	<i>ra</i>	<i>he</i>	-	<i>ra</i>	<i>ja</i>
M	-	G	G	N	-	R	-
<i>ra</i>	-	<i>m</i>	<i>Ke</i>	<i>sa</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>pa</i>	<i>r</i>
SG	RG	S	-	S	-	G	P
<i>Ta-</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>j</i>	<i>ra</i>	<i>he</i>	-	<i>si/</i>	<i>ya</i>

This tune is composed by Shri Ramasre Ji and Shri Mannulal Ji of Ayodhya which is also very popular.

Composition Style-3

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
						P	P
						<i>si</i>	<i>ya</i>
M	-	P	D	P	-	M	G
<i>Ra</i>	-	<i>ni</i>	<i>Ka</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>cha</i>	<i>la</i>	<i>su</i>
S	-	G	M	P	-	G	P
<i>ha</i>	-	<i>g</i>	<i>ra</i>	<i>he</i>	-	<i>ra</i>	<i>ja</i>
N	-	N	D	S	-	S	S
<i>ra</i>	-	<i>m</i>	<i>Ke</i>	<i>sa</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>pa</i>	<i>r</i>
N	D	N	S	N	P	P	P
<i>Ta</i>	-	<i>j</i>	<i>ra</i>	<i>he</i>	-	<i>si</i>	<i>ya</i>

Composition style 3 is in a traditional tune, which is sung by Ayodhya's locals and also by famous singers like Padmashri Malini Awasthi and Maithili Thakur.

The varying musical renditions of the same *pad*, such as “*Siya Rani ka Aanchal Suhaag Rahe*,” exemplify the depth and flexibility inherent in Ayodhya's Keertan tradition. While the core devotional sentiment remains constant, the melodic and rhythmic interpretations differ according to region, lineage, and artistic intent. This coexistence of tradition and innovation—reflected in styles ranging from locally preserved compositions to contemporary interpretations by eminent vocalists—demonstrates how Ayodhya's sacred music continues to evolve while staying rooted in its spiritual essence. Such plurality of expression not only enriches the listening experience but also sustains the emotional and communal vibrancy that lies at the heart of Keertan. Importantly, this musical analysis opens up rich avenues for future research, particularly in tracing how composition styles shift over time, reflecting a dynamic interplay between tradition and modernity in devotional music.

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